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“International hotels service in Uzbekistan”

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ABSTRACT

In fact, hotels have served as a hostel for the night since time immemorial. Today, hotels have changed not only accommodation, but also all services. There are many hotels in the world and We only know the most luxurious ones, so hotels are awarded stars based on their capacity and service they provide to customers. International hotels are cheaper and more developed than hotels in Uzbekistan, and their customer service is still at a high level. In our article, we have explored the most prestigious international hotels and hotels in Uzbekistan and we conducted questionnaires with clients.

Key words: hotels, hotel classification, international hotel service, Hotel service in Uzbekistan

INTRODUCTION

To this day, hotels serve as temporary housing. Previously, they were built in 2-room apartments. But today they not only serve as a place of temporary residence, but in addition there is a dining room, entertainment clubs, bars, ceremonial halls for weddings and events, conference rooms for scientific and business conferences.

In large hotels, if there are all types of services, then in small hotels there are some types of services. Usually small hotels provide only accommodation and meals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hotel classification:

According to international standards, hotels are classified according to the following criteria;

Star (where 1 to 5 stars are given) and letter (e.g. AAA) system

Traditional hotels - motel, hotel, guest house, boutique hotel, economy class

Modern hotels are equipped with modern interiors and equipment (rooms Division Operations by Contributors(z-lib.org) 2021)

Hotels run like a chain equal treatment of all clients, (rooms Division Author Collective Operations (z-lib.org)2021)(

International hotel service:

We can take as an example the largest hotels in the world themselves, such as – Hospitality Franchise System. Bland stone Part (USA), Holiday Inn Worldwide (UK), Best Western. International (USA), Accor (France), Choice Hotel International (USA), Marriot International (USA), Hilton Hotel Corp (USA).

US hotels rank the first place among the most popular hotels in the world. (I.ph.s.-R.S. Amriddinova, Nurullaeva Yu. 2015)

Hotel "MARRIOTT INTERNATIONAL" is one of the largest hotels in the USA. considered one of the largest multinational companies in the world according to information, ¼ of the world's tourists visit the hotel This hotel was founded in 1957. Its founder was JOHN.

MARRIOTT gave it is name, this hotel is called the Twin Bridges Marriott Hotel. In 1964, it became known as Marriott Corporation. In 1993, Marriott Corporation and Host will be called "Marriott" Marriott International Hotel Occupancy and Number of Tourist Visits 10% more than competitors in other hotels in the world. Today, Marriott International is actively developing hotels. 3,400 boat structures have been built in 66 countries outside the US services are provided to clients.

More than 150,000 employees work at Marriott International, of which 700 1000. In the future, Marriott plans to build 600 of its hotels.

it was announced that he wanted to build it.

Marriott hotel
Big boy (restaurant)
Courtyard by Marriott
Fair field Inn by Marriott
JW Marriott Hotels
JW Marriott Kuala Lumpur
Marriott ExecuStay
Marriott Hotels & Resorts
Marriott Reward
Nickelodeon Resorts by Marriott
Renaissance Inn by Marriot
The Ritz-Carlton

Spring Hall Suites

Today it operates under names such as Towne Place Suites. (http://www.worldtourism.org/wiki/Category:Marriott_International_brands) "Ritz-Carlton" This hotel has 63 branches in the world, it mainly includes resorts of the highest level.

"Renaissance Inn by Marriot" - serves corporate clients who come on business.

"Court yard by Marriott" - provides limited services, mainly located in the US and Canada. Fairfield Inn by Marriott has 392 of its hotels in the world. This is an inexpensive hotel. Spring Hall Suites is a very comfortable hotel for Woman and family Hotel "Hilton Hotels Corporation".

The Hilton Hotels was founded on May 31, 1919. Conrad Because Hilton founded Hilton named "Hilton Hotels" in 1946.

Corporation" and began to manage large projects for the sale of real estate and hotels. 2010

According to sources, the company has 3,600 hotels, more than 600,000

They say that the number of rooms exists in 81 countries. This is Hilton Hotels & Resorts,

Conrad Hotels, Doubletree, Embassy Suites Hotels, Hampton Inn, Hampton Inn & Suites,

Hilton Garden Inn, Home wood Suites by Hilton and several brands and brands. The most famous hotel in the world is the Waldorf Astoria, with only 47 rooms. This is a luxury hotel with 1508 rooms, built in the 20s in New York Avenue Park, famous people from all over the world often stay in this park.

World famous people often visit this park and up to this day, reviews of the hotel are positive. There are Peacock Alley, Bulland Bear Steakhouse and Oscar's Brasserie restaurants in the hotel and so there are other following giant hotels of the company: "Hilton New York and Towers" has 2014 rooms in Hilton Hawaiian Village (ranks 14th in the world, consists of 3386 rooms and 7 buildings),

Hilton San Francis co & Towers-(1908 rooms, 2 buildings), Hilton Chicago& Towers (consists of 1544 rooms and 3 restaurants) Hilton is one of the most famous hotel brands in the USA

– The Hilton network consists of 227 hotels and they are directly connected with each other.

Most of the clients of these hotels are well-earned and businessmen. These guests of the hotel are provided with services at the highest level.

This brand occupies a leading position in the world in improving service technologies.

- Amriddinova R.S., Nurullaeva Y. 2015)

Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide to receive tax benefits was established by the investment company Starwood Capital, during this period

the company was called Lodging. Starwood used to manage many hotels in different destinations in the northern part of the USA

Later, in 1994, he bought The Western Hotels from Japan's Aoki Corporation. In 1998, Starwood privatized the Sheraton, Four points by Sheraton and The Luxury Collection brands from ITT Sheraton.

In 1999, Starwood founded the "WHotels" logo. The guests of honor of this brand are mainly business people and the service is designed for them. By 2012, there were 500 such branded hotels. In 2005, the LeMeridien hotel chain was bought by Starwood Hotels and Resorts

This network has also ensured the successful operation of Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide in the European market.

And now Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide” has the following brands: “Westin Hotels–Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide” is the largest luxury resort.

This brand was acquired by Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide in 1994 and is one of the oldest brands (1930).

Sheraton - Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide is the most important hotel chain of the company, which was launched in 1937. (I.ph.s.-R.S. Amriddinova R.S., Nurullaeva Y. 2015)

Four Points by Sheraton is a mid-range hotel founded by ITT Sheraton. This brand was previously called "Inn", then it was merged with the name "Sheraton" and became "Four Points by Sheraton".

The brand was privatized by Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide in 1998. "The Luxury Collection" - "ITT Sheraton".

1994, CIGA (Compagnia Italiana Grandi Alberghi, or Italian Grand Hotels Company) was created after the acquisition of the Italian hotel chain.

Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide began to pay more attention to the hotels of this brand after the purchase of Sheraton. The symbol of the hotel during its previous activity was the 4 eagles of St. Markrohibi. Currently, any hotel has the right to use whichever symbol they want. became and began to create bugs.

WHotels is a subsidiary of Starwood Hotels and Resorts Worldwide is a brand of hotels in Pogon. 1998 First "W Hotels"

The hotel was opened in New York, later in Mexico, Seoul and Istanbul. Started to create a range of amenities for customers. Europe's first hotel was founded in Barcelona, Spain under the name "W Barcelona".

In 2010 in Hollywood, Texas, Taipei, Taiwan, Bali, Koh Samui, 2011 Morocco, Guangzhou, Bangkok, Paris, Athens, St. Petersburg and London the aforementioned branded hotels were built. 2012 Singapore, Milan,

Built in Oman, Abu Dhabi, Santa Fe in 2013, Cairo in 2016. planned to build a hotel.

Hotel service in Uzbekistan "HILTON"

The Hilton Hotel in Tashkent has a 5* category and has 21 floors.

There are 258 rooms in total, eight of them are presidential suites.

Received this hotel is considered one of the franchised hotels as of January 1, 2020 began to receive guests from February. The cost of one night in a hotel is from \$ 194. It was reported that it is up to \$2460. 3 Taizakaya Pan Asian in the hotel area

Restaurant and Lounge, Rush Restaurant, Tumbler Bar, Restaurant and Pool (www.google.com).

“Courtyard by Marriott”

This hotel cannot be called a 4.9* hotel. From November 30, 2020, today open seven days a week. It has 328 rooms. One night to stay at the hotel the price per night is \$139.

METHODOLOGY

As a result of research and preaching, we discovered and answered various questions:

1. About the age of visiting tourists
2. How many tourists visit hotels in Uzbekistan about

3. About whether they are satisfied with the hotel services of Uzbekistan and vice versa

4. What is the opinion of Tourists visiting Uzbekistan about hotels in Uzbekistan

5. about whether you like or dislike the services of hotels in Uzbekistan

6. About whether or not they visited other countries besides Uzbekistan

7. About Tourists' opinion about large hotels in foreign countries

8. About the importance of local residents in the further development of hotels in Uzbekistan

9. We collected answers about Measures for the further development of tourism in Uzbekistan

different opinions and discussions about the possibility of implementation

PARTICIPANTS AND DATA COLLECTION

Examples were taken at the "Courtyard by Marriott" hotel in Tashkent and at the "Hilton" hotel, located on the city square of Tashkent city, cafes, bars, restaurants, in Tashkent

International Airport, Uzbekistan Railways. The sources in the article are taken from various

Literature and from various Internet sites.

An electronic form of a questionnaire that was conducted jointly with researchers through social networks

and messengers were sent to the respondents. There were 9 questions in the questionnaires, and 35 tourists took part in this.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the answer to the first question, the majority of tourists in the questionnaire are 30-35 years old.

To our second question, almost 41% of tourists answered that they visited Uzbekistan for the first time and saw the services of hotels in Uzbekistan for the first time.

We found out that 67.7% of tourists are satisfied with the hotels in Uzbekistan. 32.3% of tourists reported that they were not satisfied.

According to our fourth question, 35.5% of tourists rated Uzbekistan hotels as satisfactory.

51.6% of tourists rated our hotels well, 12.9% of tourists rated hotels are in very good condition.

It turned out that 48.4% of tourists liked the hotel service of Uzbekistan, and 51.6% of tourists did not like it

80.6% of tourists who visited other countries compared the conditions of the hotel service in Uzbekistan and the service of other foreign countries 61% of tourists called the condition of foreign hotels very good, 19% of tourists were satisfied 19% of tourists rated it better.

On the negative impact of the local population on hotels in Uzbekistan in 29% of cases” answered “no”, in 71% of cases they answered “yes”.

In order to further develop tourism in Uzbekistan, 80% of tourists received various answers and suggestions.

The table below shows the percentage of tourists who are satisfied with hotels in Uzbekistan displayed as number

In the table, the assessment of tourists who visited hotels in foreign countries in numbers and percentages

RECOMMENDATION

According to the recommendations of tourists who took part in the survey

Further development of tourism activities in hotels in Uzbekistan

- Improving service, improving the culture of local residents,
- Paying attention to the design of hotel equipment
- It is necessary to improve the knowledge of local tourists about the norms of the law
- Development of the tourism system

- Need to work in HR
- Create broad opportunities
- Work harder and move forward
- Establishment of national values
- Make investments
- Improving the relationship of employees to customers.
- Training of qualified personnel
- Service improvement
- Increasing Conditions
- Cooking dishes and snacks according to new menus and recipes
- Make natural landscapes more comfortable
- Creation of cultural and entertainment facilities.
- Provision of hotel rooms with good conditions
- Give advice and recommendations on how the Employees work and on developing the skills of the employees

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

According to the conduct of the survey and the results obtained, proposals for the further development of the Hotels of Uzbekistan should be implemented and it is being considered to gradually implement all these proposals in the future in the field of tourism.

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